

Crisis Lessons Relearned: Uncertainty, Credit Tightening, and Default Dynamics from 2008 to COVID-19

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Abstract

Successive shocks from the Global Financial Crisis and COVID-19, renewed U.S.–China trade tensions under the Trump administration, and rapid advances in AI have contributed to geoeconomic uncertainty becoming a central factor in decision-making and planning within the financial sector. However, to date, systematic evidence linking economic policy uncertainty (EPU) to banking-sector risk and performance outcomes remains limited. This study synthesises evidence on how EPU affects bank credit risk by drawing from nine empirical studies spanning both advanced and emerging economies. The study identifies three consistent patterns across all the studies. First, a higher EPU is associated with higher NPL ratios. Second, bank characteristics (e.g., solvency, profitability, size/ownership) and market structure (concentration) mediate the effect of uncertainty on NPLs. Third, information transparency and digital transformation are crucial tools for mitigating the adverse effects of uncertainty on credit default risk.

“The probability of a banking crisis (beginning) conditional on financial liberalisation is higher than the unconditional probability.” Kaminsky and Reinhart, 1999.

Introduction

Since the pandemic, the proportion of non-performing loans (NPLs) relative to total gross loans has increased in both emerging and advanced economies, often serving as an early warning sign of banking sector stress (Čihák & Schaeck, 2010; Ari & Ratnovski, 2019). From 2019 to 2024, the overall NPL ratios grew by approximately 65% in emerging markets, compared to 15% in advanced economies (Figure 1), highlighting a disproportionate risk of financial instability in emerging markets (FRED, 2019; CEIC data, 2024; Helgi Library, 2024; Trading Economics, 2024; World Bank, 2024).

Figure 1: The ratio of NPLs across emerging and advanced economies.

A typical structural pattern has emerged across past systemic disruptions, from the 1994 Tequila Crisis to the 2008 Global Financial Crisis, the 2010–2012 European Sovereign Debt Crisis, and the COVID-19 pandemic: a surge in uncertainty regarding macroprudential shifts triggers credit contractions, rising interest rates, and borrower distress, ultimately leading to sharp increases in NPLs. While banks rationally raise interest rates to hedge against policy uncertainty (Baker et al., 2016), this response may prove counterproductive. Firms facing higher debt-service costs—particularly those with pre-existing liquidity constraints (Bernanke et al., 1999)—become more likely to default, which in turn raises NPL ratios (Claessens et al., 2020). This creates an adverse

feedback loop (Tangngisalu et al., 2020; Kiyotaki & Moore, 1997), where rising NPLs further constrain liquidity (Diamond & Rajan, 2001) and credit supply, deepening economic slowdowns (Bordo et al., 2016; Klein, 2013). Elevated NPLs also destabilise the banking sector through multiple channels. When banks face higher credit risk due to loan defaults, they tend to reallocate their balance sheet and managerial resources from intermediation to recovery, thereby creating operational inefficiencies (Berger & DeYoung, 1997). It also increases stress on the bank's profitability by reducing net interest margins through provisions (Brunnermeier, 2009).

Figure 2: The trend of Global Economic Policy Uncertainty from 2019 to 2025.

Source: *Global Economic Policy Uncertainty (GEPU) Index*, Davis (2016), policyuncertainty.com, accessed August 4, 2025.

Since 2020, the global economy has faced unprecedented uncertainty due to multiple simultaneous shocks (Figure 2), including supply chain disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (Guerrieri et al., 2022), geopolitical instability from the Russia-Ukraine conflict (Caldara & Iacoviello, 2022; Smales, 2021; Ahmed et al., 2023), and ongoing U.S.-China trade and technology disputes (Fajgelbaum & Khandelwal, 2022). As a result, the Global Economic Policy Uncertainty (GEPU) Index has increased to record levels, reaching 507 in 2025Q2 - a 142% rise compared to the 2010-2019 average (Baker et al., 2025). The situation in the United States appears particularly bleak, with the highest reading (725 in April) in the 40-year history of uncertainty measurement (1985-2025). It reflects the growing interconnectedness of geopolitical tensions and financial market instability following these recent crises.

Although existing literature (e.g., Nkusu, 2011; Klein, 2013; Louzis et al., 2012) emphasises macroeconomic factors such as GDP, inflation, and unemployment as key determinants of non-performing loans, there is limited research examining the impact of economic policy uncertainty on banks' credit risk during and after systemic crises. The ambiguity surrounding the government's future actions in the monetary, fiscal, and

regulatory sectors has a direct and significant influence on investment, lending, borrowers' repayment capacity, and the overall stability of financial markets. While previous studies have focused on the United States (Bordo et al., 2016) and the euro area (Karadima & Louri, 2021; Zeqiraj et al., 2024), this study addresses the open question of how economic uncertainty affects credit risk in emerging economies, with a particular focus on South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. Therefore, the contribution of this study to the academic literature on financial stability and economic resilience is twofold. First, this study aims to provide a focused mini-review that investigates the mechanism linking macroeconomic (policy) uncertainty to bank loan default. The second part of the study derives the evidence into actionable policy measures to manage and reduce NPL exposure under heightened uncertainty.

The rest of the study is organised as follows: Section 2 outlines the conceptual foundations of EPU and NPL. Section 3 reviews the literature on the role of and uncertainty measured by EPU in bank credit risk. Section 4 describes the methodology and presents the results. Section 5 concludes with policy recommendations based on the research findings.

2. Definitions and Measurement of Terms

This section defines conceptual terms and measurement options for the key variables. In this study, macroeconomic uncertainty is measured by the EPU index, while credit risk is proxied by the non-performing loan (NPL) ratio (Chaibi & Ftiti, 2015).

i. Non-Performing Loan ratio (NPL)

Several studies have identified the non-performing loan ratio as a reliable and comprehensive indicator for evaluating credit risk related to banking sector vulnerability (Naili & Lahrichi, 2022; Moinescu, 2012; Palmer, 2015). According to the IMF Compilation Guide of Financial Soundness Indicators, a loan is deemed non-performing when the interest or principal payment is overdue by 90 days or more (IMF, 2005; European Central Bank, 2017). The study concentrates on the bank's non-performing loans to gross loans (%) as the dependent variable.

ii. Economic Policy Uncertainty Index (EPU)

The modelling and structuring of the newspaper-based EPU index have been developed by Baker et al. (2016). This index has been constructed using three components which capture the multidimensional uncertainty and cover the period from 1997 to the present for 22 countries. First, the news-based component, carrying 50% weight, tracks the newspaper coverage of policy-related economic uncertainty from ten leading newspapers by tracing three sets of terms. The first group of keywords includes terms like “economy” and “economic”; the second group captures variations of the word “uncertainty,” such as “uncertain” and “uncertainty”; and the third group consists of policy-related terms, including “policy,” “regulation,” “Federal Reserve,” “tax,”

“spend,” “budget,” and “deficit.” For a robustness check, the authors also employed the same approach for the news-based macroeconomic uncertainty index by using Google News. Second, a scheduled tax code expiration index, weighting 25% is based on the uncertainty surrounding the future expiration of federal tax rules, which often involves delayed decisions by policymakers, placing households and businesses in a state of uncertainty about whether to invest or not. This numeric index was developed using data on all tax code rules scheduled to expire within the next 10 years, provided by the Congressional Budget Office (CBO). To create this index, the authors calculated the value of the discounted sum of these future expirations, weighted by their dollar impacts. The authors used the forecaster disagreement index as their final component, which was critically based on the range of disagreement among fifty professional economic forecasters each quarter regarding the outcome of changes in the price level and government purchases. By combining all three components, the authors have developed a monthly index that reflects the evolving nature of monetary and fiscal uncertainty caused by policy implications.

3. Methodology

This brief review on the impact of macroeconomic policy ambiguity on bank non-performing loans is suitable for presentations to central banks. The primary question of this study is: how, and under what conditions, does economic policy uncertainty (EPU) influence the formation and dynamics of banks' non-performing loans (NPLs)? This study focuses on commercial banks and banking systems in advanced and emerging economies from 1990 to August 13, 2025 (Sydney time). Policy Uncertainty exposures include established indices such as the Baker-Bloom-Davis EPU, the World Uncertainty Index (WUI), and the Jurado-Ludvigson-Ng (JLN) macroeconomic uncertainty index. To measure credit risk exposure, this study employs the percentage of non-performing loans to total gross loans as the primary indicator, a common metric for default probability among financial institutions. To establish the quantitative relationship between EPU and NPLs, this study strictly relies on widely accepted econometric methods. These include panel and time-series regressions (FE/RE; IV/system-GMM), local projections, VAR/VECM, difference-in-differences, threshold models, and other dynamic panel techniques. Furthermore, this study avoids research lacking an uncertainty metric, outcomes unrelated to bank credit risk, purely descriptive crisis narratives, duplicated samples when a better method exists, and non-English full texts due to resource constraints.

The articles under review were systematically collected from the Scopus database using a structured search protocol. To investigate the link between Economic Policy Uncertainty (EPU) and Non-Performing Loans (NPLs), articles were identified through Boolean keyword combinations (e.g., ("economic policy uncertainty" OR "EPU") AND ("non-performing loans" OR "NPL" OR "credit risk")), followed by careful screening of titles and abstracts. The final sample, which includes nine studies explicitly examining EPU-NPL transmission

channels, is presented in Tables 1 and 2 to emphasise the conceptual, methodological, and contextual aspects of this literature.

Table 1. Journal and Publisher Distribution

	Article Name	Author (s)	Journal	Publisher	Year	Scopus IF (CiteScore)
1	Economic policy uncertainty and non-performing loans: The moderating role of bank concentration	Maria Karadima; Helen Louri	Finance Research Letters.	Elsevier	2021	4.66
2	Economic uncertainty, public debt and non-performing loans in the Eurozone: Three systemic crises	Veton Zeqiraj; Constantin Gurdgiev; Kazi Sohag; Shawkat Hammoudeh	International Review of Financial Analysis	Elsevier	2024	2.35
3	Economic policy uncertainty, credit risks and banks' lending decisions: Evidence from Chinese commercial banks	Qinwei Chi; Wenjing Li	China Journal of Accounting Research	Sun Yat-sen Medical University	2017	3.03
4	Economic Policy Uncertainty Effects on Credit and Stability of Financial Institutions	Mustafa Caglayan; Bing Xu	Bulletin of Economic Research	John Wiley and Sons Inc	2019	2.51

5	Economic policy uncertainty and the risk of Chinese commercial banks	Weishu Jing; Cody Yu-Ling Hsiao	Finance Research Letters	Elsevier	2025	N/A
6	The effect of Economic Policy Uncertainty on the credit risk of US commercial banks	Carmen Orden-Cruz; Jessica Paule-Vianez; Júlio Lobão	International Journal of Finance and Economics	John Wiley and Sons Ltd	2023	1.70
7	Does Uncertainty Affect the Banks' Non-Performing Loans/Non-Performing Finance in the MENA Region?	Shadi R. M. Aledeimat; Murad Abdurahman Bein	SAGE Open	SAGE Publications Inc.	2025	N/A
8	Policy uncertainty and non-performing loans in Greece	Stephanos Papadamou; Konstantinos Pitsilkas	American Journal of Economics and Sociology	John Wiley and Sons Inc	2025	N/A
9	Impacts of economic policy uncertainty (EPU) and institutional quality (IQ) on bank risk-taking behaviour	Syed Moudud-Ul-Huq; Runa Akter	Kybernetes	Emerald	2024	N/A

Table 2. Articles' Category Based on the Subject

	Article Name	Objectives	Findings	Recommendations
1	Economic Policy Uncertainty and Non-Performing Loans: The Moderating Role of Bank Concentration	To examine the effect of economic policy uncertainty on non-performing loans and the moderating role of bank consolidation in Eurozone banks (a study of 507 banks across France, Germany, Italy, and Spain from 2005 to 2017, using a two-step System GMM approach).	Economic uncertainty has a positive impact on NPLs. However, greater bank concentration significantly weakens this effect: in more consolidated banking systems, the surge in NPLs under high uncertainty is notably smaller.	Bank consolidation can be a valuable tool for reducing credit risk under uncertainty by improving information screening and diversification. However, increasing concentration alone cannot eliminate risk, and further structural reforms are necessary to maintain financial stability.
2	Economic uncertainty, public debt and non-performing loans in the Eurozone: Three systemic crises.	To examine how EPU interacts with systemic crises to affect bank credit risk using data from 194 banks across 19 Eurozone countries (2001–2021), covering the Global Financial Crisis, European debt crisis, and COVID-19 crisis. This study uses the following methods: i. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) with two-way clustered standard errors	Economic policy uncertainty increases credit risk during systemic crises. Higher EPU consistently leads to increased NPL formation in crisis periods. However, the effect of the crisis on loan default varies considerably during each event. The study shows that rapid policy responses (e.g., fiscal support, central bank actions) significantly reduced the impact of uncertainty on NPLs	Banks and policymakers should frequently update crisis management plans. Rather than solely relying on past crisis strategies, they must account for the unique features of each new crisis.

		<p>ii. Fixed effects estimations</p> <p>iii. Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) estimations</p>	<p>during the COVID-19 pandemic compared to those in crises from 2008 to 2014.</p>	
3	<p>Economic policy uncertainty, credit risks and banks' lending decisions: Evidence from Chinese commercial banks</p>	<p>To assess how economic policy uncertainty affects the credit risks and lending decisions of Chinese banks (using the OLS regression technique for the data from 2000 to 2014).</p>	<p>Higher EPU leads to notably higher non-performing loan ratios and more concentrated loan portfolios. It indicates increased credit risk and slower loan growth. Government-owned banks were less affected, while the impact was more significant in joint-stock banks, signalling higher risk exposure.</p>	<p>Banks can sustain stability during periods of high uncertainty by reducing loan growth and exposure.</p> <p>Increased marketisation and financial depth in the economy help moderate the impact of policy uncertainty on credit risk.</p>
4	<p>Economic Policy Uncertainty Effects on Credit and Stability of Financial Institutions</p>	<p>To investigate EPU's impact on credit availability and bank stability (non-performing loans) using a panel of 18 countries (1985–2013). The study employs an instrumental variables estimator based on the generalised method of moments (IV-GMM).</p>	<p>Rising uncertainty significantly reduces credit supply and increases NPLs. For every 10% increase in EPU, banks' loan growth falls (approx. 0.2–0.6%) while NPL ratios rise (~1%) on average (effects vary by country resources and regulations).</p>	<p>The authors suggest that healthier bank balance sheets and adequate supervision can reduce the effects of policy uncertainty.</p> <p>Strong capital buffers and robust regulatory frameworks help maintain credit flow even in the face of high uncertainty.</p>

5	<p>Economic policy uncertainty and the risk of Chinese commercial banks</p>	<p>To analyse the impact of EPU on various risk dimensions (credit risk, operational risk, etc.) of Chinese commercial banks (110 banks, 2010–2021), and whether digital transformation moderates these effects.</p>	<p>Higher EPU significantly exacerbates banks' credit and operational risks, while simultaneously making banks more risk-averse (lower risk-taking).</p> <p>The negative impact is more pronounced for smaller banks than for large banks, due to their weaker information networks and risk management capacities.</p> <p>Digital transformation in banking is found to mitigate the adverse impact of EPU on risk levels effectively.</p>	<p>Policymakers should consider targeted support for smaller banks (e.g. liquidity lines, countercyclical capital buffers) during highly uncertain periods.</p> <p>Banks should also focus on enhancing information quality and risk management to prevent premature deleveraging.</p>
6	<p>The effect of Economic Policy Uncertainty on the credit risk of US commercial banks</p>	<p>Assess the impact of EPU on credit risk in US banks, differentiating by bank size, profitability, and capital solvency (a study of 2,994 U.S. banks, 2017–2019 panel using fixed effect estimation)</p>	<p>Elevated policy uncertainty is associated with a significant rise in NPLs in U.S. commercial banks.</p> <p>Banks with lower profitability or weaker capital ratios experience a much larger increase in NPLs during high EPU periods (e.g., less profitable banks encounter approximately 22% higher NPL growth under a one-standard-deviation EPU shock).</p>	<p>Bank regulators and managers should emphasise maintaining higher profitability and a solvency ratio to withstand periods of high uncertainty.</p> <p>Future research should investigate additional factors (such as broader periods and various regions), given the inconclusive role of size and the study's focus on the U.S.</p>

			<p>In contrast, highly solvent banks experience comparatively smaller increases in NPLs during periods of uncertainty. The size of the bank alone does not affect EPU vulnerability.</p>	
7	<p>Does Uncertainty Affect the Banks' Non-Performing Loans/Non-Performing Finance in the MENA Region?</p>	<p>To compare the impacts of uncertainty on NPLs in the Middle East and North Africa's (MENA) conventional vs. Islamic banks. The study covers 92 banks in 13 MENA countries (2005–2022) and considers both global EPU and US monetary policy uncertainty effects.</p>	<p>The results show mixed effects of uncertainty: higher global economic policy uncertainty is linked to increased NPLs in MENA banks, while greater US monetary policy uncertainty is unexpectedly associated with lower NPL levels in the region.</p> <p>MENA banks respond to uncertainty by adopting cautious lending practices – for example, requiring more collateral and reducing loan-to-value ratios during volatile periods.</p>	<p>Banks in the MENA region should tailor their risk management strategies to various sources of uncertainty, such as global versus US policy changes, as their impacts can differ significantly.</p> <p>However, the contrasting NPL outcomes under global versus US uncertainty remain puzzling and unexplained in the study, indicating potential asymmetric spillover effects.</p> <p>Policymakers in emerging economies should monitor both local and international sources of uncertainty and strengthen domestic financial</p>

				regulations accordingly to manage the simultaneous and sometimes conflicting influences on bank stability.
8	Policy uncertainty and non-performing loans in Greece	To investigate the long-run and short-run relationships between policy uncertainty and non-performing loans in Greece (using 2002–2020 quarterly data, 75 observations) and across different loan segments, via a VECM approach.	Economic policy uncertainty has a significant positive impact on NPL ratios in Greece, both in the short and long term. When the total NPL ratio is disaggregated, consumer loan NPLs adjust the slowest to long-run equilibrium after a shock, while mortgage NPLs adjust the fastest.	Banks and regulators should pay special attention to consumer lending, as consumer NPLs are slower to recover. Targeted strategies (such as debt restructuring or support programs for consumer loans) may be needed under prolonged uncertainty.
9	Impacts of economic policy uncertainty (EPU) and institutional quality (IQ) on bank risk-taking behaviour	To evaluate the effects of economic policy uncertainty and institutional quality on banks' risk-taking behaviour, using 4,367 banks across 27 countries (2011–2020) and dynamic panel GMM estimation.	Higher EPU prompts banks to take more aggressive risks, evidenced by rising non-performing loan ratios. In contrast, strong institutional quality (IQ)—such as improved governance, regulatory standards, and especially “voice and accountability”—significantly reduces bank risk-taking. In countries with solid institutions, banks are less prone to take excessive	The study highlights that improving institutional quality (governance and transparency) can mitigate banks' risk-taking amid economic uncertainty. Policymakers should focus on strengthening governance indicators (such as voice and accountability, regulatory effectiveness) to curb excessive risk-taking in

			risks amid high uncertainty, whereas weak institutional settings foster riskier behaviours.	the banking sector during uncertain times.
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4. Results and Discussion

This research is limited to reviewing only nine journal articles due to the scarcity of studies on how uncertainty regarding future policy changes influences borrower behaviour. The reviewed studies quantify a policy-uncertainty → credit-tightening channel, with rate and regulatory shocks linked to contractionary lending and stricter funding conditions. The following discussion interprets these effects and examines their implications for loan default dynamics.

i. Direct Impact of EPU on NPLs Across Banking Systems

Cross-country evidence suggests that higher economic policy uncertainty (EPU) is associated with increased non-performing loan (NPL) ratios in banks across both advanced and emerging economies. For instance, in a panel of 18 countries, Caglayan & Xu (2019) report that a 10% increase in EPU is linked to approximately a 1% rise in the NPL ratio. Within the euro area, panel estimates also display similar outcomes. During periods of heightened policy uncertainty, loan quality declines significantly, leading to higher NPL ratios (Karadima & Louri, 2021; Zeqiraj et al., 2024). Country-specific data support this trend. In the United States, Orden-Cruz et al. (2023) find that policy uncertainty has a significant positive effect on credit risk. They show that an EPU shock of one unit causes an overall increase of 8.9% in NPLs, with medium-sized banks facing an even larger rise of 13.6%. Likewise, Papadamou & Pitsilkas (2025) indicate that in Greece, policy uncertainty significantly raises NPL levels in both the short and long term.

Emerging market research shows a similar positive link between policy uncertainty and non-performing loans. In China, banks exhibit increased risk aversion and slower loan growth during periods of heightened policy uncertainty (Chi & Li, 2017). This leads to a build-up of credit risk in the banking sector. Both conventional and Islamic banks have demonstrated higher borrower default rates during periods of greater uncertainty in the MENA region (Aledeimat, 2025). This study highlights source-dependent asymmetric uncertainty effects. The authors document that global policy uncertainty is associated with higher domestic NPLs, whereas U.S. monetary-policy uncertainty correlates with lower NPLs. This finding is consistent with banks tightening credit ex ante and improving portfolio composition (Valencia, 2017; Dixit & Pindyck, 1994).

ii. Moderating Factors

These studies further demonstrate that balance-sheet strength and industry structure influence the positive relationship between uncertainty and the NPL ratio. During periods of uncertainty, banks struggle to accurately assess borrowers' creditworthiness, leading to a less effective screening process. Consequently, uncertainty undermines underwriting quality and increases default risk across economies (Berger & DeYoung, 1997). Evidence from the Euro area (Karadima & Louri, 2021) and China (Chi & Li, 2017; Jing et al., 2025) suggests that larger and more consolidated banks are more effective in mitigating the impact of uncertainty on non-performing loans. Jing et al. (2025) also emphasise that small and medium-sized banks are more vulnerable to credit risk during policy shifts. These findings support the notion that, in times of uncertainty, larger banks tend to maintain their asset quality, thereby enabling them to implement more robust risk management strategies. Conversely, smaller banks face greater difficulties in assessing borrowers' creditworthiness due to limited information networks. Studies suggest that bank ownership structure influences how policy-related shocks are absorbed. State-owned banks appear less sensitive to uncertainty shocks related to NPL formation than private banks, reflecting implicit government backing and more cautious risk management amid uncertain conditions.

Empirical research indicates that policy uncertainty is a significant factor influencing NPL dynamics during systemic crises (Zeqiraj et al., 2024). During such times, uncertainty serves as an early warning for rising loan defaults. However, prompt policy measures by central banks and governments can substantially reduce these negative effects. Despite increased uncertainty, European banks saw smaller rises in the NPL ratio during the COVID-19 crisis compared to the 2008–09 crisis. This evidence suggests that effective crisis management policies can stabilise credit markets by reducing the link between uncertainty and defaults.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

“Uncertainty is the only certainty there is, and knowing how to live with insecurity is the only security.”

— *John Allen Paulos*

This literature review summarises evidence that banking sectors face increased borrower default risk due to uncertainty from various policy sources. The study finds that bank fundamentals (capitalisation, solvency, profitability, size/ownership) and market concentration mitigate the impact of policy uncertainty on NPL accumulation. Moreover, institutions with weaker borrower screening tend to show a higher NPL ratio due to information asymmetry. However, researchers warn that each crisis and institutional context may pose unique challenges to the banking sector and credit system. Ultimately, these studies emphasise that sound regulatory policy, robust governance, and effective crisis management are vital for reducing credit risk caused by economic policy uncertainty.

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